

DI.3 DIAMOND Communication Plan

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Executive Summary

Eurecat is responsible for designing and implementing DIAMOND communication strategy through its Research Communications Office, but all consortium partners will be involved in it. This deliverable details the communication plan, aiming at raising awareness of as many relevant actors as possible on the activities and results derived from the project in order to: promote and position the project results; reach and involve where possible the transport industry, transport professionals and society at large (general public), to support the exploitation of project results.

The channels considered in the communication plan are: designing the project’s corporate identity, social media channels, official website, promotional materials (brochure, flyers, posters), media relations and email marketing.

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Terminology and Acronyms

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FP	Framework Programme
PMB	Project Management Board
PMP	Project Management Plan
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
STAB	Scientific and Technical Advisory Board
WP	Work Package

[This table must be organized in alphabetical order once you have finished including items.]

Introduction

DIAMOND is a 3-year Research and Innovation Action (RIA) aiming to establish new knowledge to support women's inclusion in European current and future transport systems.

DIAMOND Communication Plan aims at raising awareness of as many relevant actors as possible on the project activities and results.

The channels and activities considered in the plan are: develop projects' corporate visual identity, manage social media channels, set up an official website, design promotional materials (brochure, flyers, posters), media relations and produce email marketing campaigns, among other activities or channels that may be used throughout the project.

It is worth noting that in order to protect the commercial interests of the participants, the publication of the materials will be selective, except for submission of contractually required reports and information to the Commission. In this case, partners decide which part of the projects' information is to be protected by copyright or trade secrets and which part of the above information is suitable for communicating widely.

Eurecat leads DIAMOND communication activity within the project, through its Research Communications Office, but all consortium partners will be involved in it. We understand communication as a continuous process that needs to be seen as essential for the results of the project, itself.

All the actions will consider EC recommendations explained in the Participant Portal H2020 Online Manual section on project communication.
(http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm).

Key messages

The communication plan messages have been **carefully designed and tailored with each of the stakeholders** in mind and will be adapted to the different DIAMOND communication channels. The messages go together with the main objectives and translate the possibilities and strength of the research done during the project.

The following messages will be **evolved in pertinent messages for all audiences**, both specialized and non-specialized, in a way that they can understand actions and results of DIAMOND project.

The messages that DIAMOND will address to stakeholders include:

- Getting data for the understanding of women's needs, motivations, talent and expectations on different transport models and technologies can **benefit transport operators and organisers to improve their services and new transport technologies' implementation.**

- DIAMOND supports transport organisers and operators in **turning data into actionable knowledge** with notions of fairness by providing recommendations on concrete measures, and assessing their impact on fairness and on their businesses.
- DIAMOND provides a **novel integrated platform on all available datasets and research results on women’s needs, motivations and talent in transport and mobility.**
- The project is funded by the European Commission, who believes that DIAMOND will contribute to increasing the inclusion of women in mobility and transport systems.

Audience

The audience for Communication action is the same as identified for Dissemination and Exploitation, as broken down in several main stakeholder groups below:

Businesses / Operators	Scientific, academic and educational community	Government / authorities	Associations and advocates	Society in general
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public or private transport operators / service providers. • Vehicle manufacturers and their providers (Tier1). • Car-sharing companies. • Bicycle rental operators. • New mobility services providers/start-ups • Transport consultants. • Data specialists and technology consultants. • Engineering and infrastructure design companies. • Head-hunters, HR agencies. • Insurance companies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research institutions in transport, gender, sociology-related areas. • Decision-makers and HR staff from universities, vocational / training centres. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elected officials at EU, national, regional and local level. • Policy makers at EU, national and local levels (Women in Transport Platform). • Transport planners and strategists. • Public transport operators and transport organisers. • HR managers, health and safety. • Traffic police, emergency services. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport-related associations / advocates. • Gender-related associations/advocates. • Trade Unions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communities (local interest groups, cycling/walking groups, public transport user groups, local authority forums). • Transport of gender-related NGOs. • Media / bloggers. • Individual citizens.

Figure 1: DIAMOND communication stakeholders

The process of identifying the key persons and entities that embody this stakeholder consideration has already begun, developing a more detailed list to be the target for all communication activities. All stakeholders with a professional Twitter account will be followed by DIAMOND’s Twitter.

Channels

For communication activities, DIAMOND project will use a wide range of channels and actions, covering from promotional materials to media relations, using email marketing campaigns, setting up a website and building a community of interested users around the project (see Figure 1).

Besides the ones mentioned, all partners will make use of their channels (website, presence on Social Media and corporate newsletters / publications) to communicate news about DIAMOND and reach a broader audience.

Figure 2 .DIAMOND communication channels

4.1 Project's Corporate Visual Identity

Eurecat, as the leader of Communication task has developed DIAMOND's Corporate Visual Identity, including the project's logo, a Power Point template, Word templates for project activities and a visual identity standards guidebook, defining and outlining how to use identifying elements pertaining to DIAMOND including logos, colours, fonts, stationery and some marketing advertising materials.

Following the project's visual identity manual, in the **M5**, a **poster layout** following DIAMOND visual image will be produced.

4.1.1 DIAMOND Logo

DIAMOND logo aims to represent the different concepts surrounding the project. As pictured in figure 2, DIAMOND's logo shape symbolizes the project's research methodology, as well as a polyhedral diamond, a location pin map, and the ideas of mobility and network of data nodes.

Figure 3: Full color and negative version of the logo

Figure 4: DIAMOND concepts represented in logo figure

4.1.2 Visual Corporate Identity (VCI) manual

A visual identity and standards guidebook has been produced and distributed among partners to ensure that project's branding is not compromised and all partners use the elements properly in order to convey the properties and goals of the project as a brand.

Partners have to treat the guidebook as a source of the materials and instructions as a basis for further development of the project's materials. See below some parts of the manual:

Figure 5: DIAMOND project colours

Special Font
for promotional
items

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Montserrat>

Montserrat Regular

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGRHIJKLOMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 0123456789

Text Font
for promotional
items

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Montserrat>

Montserrat Light

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGRHIJKLOMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 0123456789

Montserrat medium

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGRHIJKLOMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 0123456789

Montserrat Bold

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGRHIJKLOMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 0123456789

Text Font
for deliverable
and presentations
items **only**

Gill Sans Regular

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 0123456789

Gill Sans Semibold

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 0123456789

Figure 6: DIAMOND fonts for promotional materials, deliverables and presentations.

Figure 7: Graphic resources for designing project's materials.

4.1.3 Word Templates

Communication Leader Eurecat has prepared two Word templates, which have been shared with partners: one for deliverables and another one to be used for minutes, meetings' agenda and other purposes. These materials will be used throughout all the project's execution to maintain a coherent and consistent image.

Figure 8: View of some pages of the project's deliverable template.

Figure 9: Word template for minutes, meeting’s agenda and other.

4.1.4 Power Point Template

A Power Point template has been designed to be used for all project’s internal and external presentations.

Figure 10: Slides of DIAMOND's power point template.

4.2 Website

According to the work plan, Euratec is responsible for designing and implementing the official DIAMOND project website, to be launch on M4 (February 2019). The registered URL is www.diamond-project.eu.

The sections hereinafter describe the web platform. The website is the **anchor for all communication activities** related to the project and serve as a **central point of entry for all public material, including the project’s basic information, all project-related resources/results generated (white paper, models toolbox, guidelines, etc. to be downloaded) and public deliverables**. The website will be continuously updated with news, links to other relevant sites, details of published papers, conferences and exhibitions during the project and will remain active during two years after the project’s finalisation.

The website platform will follow the corporate visual identity of the project created by Eurecat and approved by partners and it will give access to DIAMOND social media channels (Twitter and Youtube).

Considering that different authors might update the site, a Content Management System has been adopted, to easily and quickly publish the content. Eurecat proposes to use **Wordpress**, as the Eurecat’s Research Communication Office has wide experience with this CMS.

Regarding the website languages, the basis is English but if a need to translate some parts of the website arise, a **multilingual plugin will be installed** for this purpose.

It is essential that the website is optimised for browsing on tablets and smart phones, so the website has been developed using a **responsive design** approach.

4.2.1 Website structure

Eurecat proposes the following Information architecture for DIAMOND website:

Figure 11: Structure of DIAMOND’s website main menu

4.2.2 Contents

The texts hereinafter are the contents that will be published in the website.

4.2.2.1 Home

It includes 2 sliders with the project’s title **“Revealing fair and actionable knowledge from data to support women’s inclusion in transport systems”** and main claim **“Addressing gender-specific needs in Europe’s current and future transport systems”**.

The homepage also includes a short description of the project, a section with key expected outputs of the project and a **call to action that will be changed regularly depending on the needs of the project** (e.g. form for building a community of users interested in DIAMOND, register to the newsletter, data collection questionnaire, to download any of the project’s results – guidelines, whitepaper -, register to a DIAMOND workshop, etc.).

In addition, it will be designed a section mentioning the consortium linking to the consortium page.

As soon as the “News / Blog” sections have some articles it will be created a section at the homepage showing the latest publications, together with the project’s twitter feed and upcoming events in which the project will participate.

DIAMOND Project

A European reference tool for obtaining knowledge, recommendations and support on gender inclusion in current and future transport systems.

DIAMOND project analyses and converts data into knowledge with notions of impartiality to move towards a more inclusive and efficient transportation system from a gender perspective.

The project identifies and evaluates specific measures to meet the needs and expectations of women as users of different modes of transport and as workers in the sector.

Advances in the state-of-the art

- Holistic research on women in transport.
- Methods for gender analysis.
- Fairness applied to women in transport analysis.
- Novel self-diagnosis and decision support system (DSS) tools.

4 case studies from a gender perspective

- **Railways and public multimodal transport:** Needs and expectations in terms of safety inside a station, accessibility and comfort.
- **Automated and interconnected vehicles:** Requirements in comfort and safety in autonomous vehicles.
- **Vehicle sharing:** Needs and expectations in the planning of vehicle sharing services (types of vehicles, fleet location and planning).
- **Corporate social responsibility and employment:** Women participation in the transport sector crossed with concrete job positions.

Consortium

The DIAMOND consortium is composed by 14 partners from 8 European countries.

Spain, UK, Italy, Belgrade, Poland, France, Turkey, Ireland. A well-balanced consortium combining the main actors of the whole mobility and transport value chain.

4.2.2.2 About DIAMOND

This section includes the main information about the project, the main goal and the expected impact. A link to download the project’s infosheet is included. As more promotional materials are designed (leaflet, rollups, etc.) a specific page within the website will be created to allocate them.

It is divided in the following sub-sections/areas:

The project

Revealing actionable knowledge from data for more inclusive and efficient transport systems.

DIAMOND project analyses and converts data into knowledge with notions of impartiality to support gender inclusion in current and future transport systems from the perspective of women as transport users and as professionals in the sector.

The project makes use of data mining and analytics, together with the use of elicitation techniques in order to gather and analyse gender desegregated data, including new sources, to identify, design and evaluate specific measurements for fulfilling women's needs and expectations from the transport sector.

The knowledge gathered is to be fed into a self-diagnose tool, a practical decision support tool and for the production of diverse materials, providing recommendations on how to achieve fair gender inclusiveness in different scenarios and promoting female employment in the sector.

Start: November 2018 – **End:** October 2021

European transport sector key figures

- 11 million jobs in Europe in the transport sector.
- Generating €548bn in gross value added overall for the 28 EU countries.
- Only 22% of transport workers are women.

A Word from DIAMOND's technical coordinator

We envision DIAMOND to become the platform of reference in the whole transport sector for transport planners, researchers and for the broader public, feeding the datasets and updating guidelines continuously, towards a universalization of the conclusions of the analysis.

- Francisco Santarremigia, PhD in Transport and Logistics.
DIAMOND's technical coordinator.

DIAMOND Data Model

(picture of inclusive DIAMOND polyhedron shape)

- **Transport infrastructure and business models today:** Analysis of women's needs and travel patterns, how transport models and infrastructure have been designed based on these requirements.
- **User of vehicles today:** Analysis of the current design and potential design improvements in vehicles currently being used.

- **Jobholder today:** Analysis of the factors that directly influence in current gender unbalance in the transport and mobility sector to generate a more inclusive mobility and transport system.
- **Future transport infrastructure and business models:** Gender patterns identification and measurement in the acceptance and resistance to new infrastructures and business models for transport mobility solutions.
- **User of vehicles tomorrow:** Identifications of gender patterns in the acceptance and resistance to the vehicles of the future.
- **Future jobholders:** Investigation of estimated variations between both genders about talents and skills demanded for professional careers in the transport sector in the year 2050.

Beyond current's state-of-the-art outputs

- **Holistic research on women in transport:** Analysis in areas of transport such as women as a vehicle user and women as a jobholder today and in the future, going beyond current studies with results based not only in sociological and psychological data but also on real data analyses through computer algorithms.
- **Methods for gender analysis:** Development of multi-level models to explain the travel behaviour of different sub-groups of women and of women's employment in transport from a socio-economics, demographic and psychological perspectives.
- **Fairness applied to women in transport analysis:** Adaptation of traditional and widely recognized definitions of fairness to DIAMOND's model and case studies by designing data analysis algorithms that incorporate parameters, weights and constraints avoiding gender bias.
- **Novel self-diagnosis and DSS tools:** Self-diagnosis toolbox and a decision support system (DSS) able to detect weaknesses in a specific transport planner in terms of fairness, suggest specific recommendations and assess their impact in their business operation.

Validation with key transport operators

DIAMOND results to be proven in four specific public and private transport sectors, representative of the main mobility modes.

- **Railways and public multimodal transport:** Research study on stations safety, accessibility and comfort from a gender perspective. Validation of the self-diagnose and DSS tool for infrastructure and transport service planning.
- **Automated and interconnected vehicles:** Analysis of the comfort and safety of automated vehicles to adapt the design and functionality of electronic stability controllers (ESC) to gender through algorithms and machine learning.

- **Vehicle sharing:** Evidence of needs and requirements in the planning of vehicle sharing services addressing gender. Validation and diagnosis of DIAMOND's Decision Support System for vehicles points and fleet distribution and location planning.
- **Corporate social responsibility and employment:** Research on women's participation in the transport and logistics sectors crossed with concrete job positions and new opportunities to translate this understanding into concrete better gender-oriented job descriptions and use of adapted candidate search processes.

4.2.2.2.1 Consortium

Section devoted to the partners' corporate information, including their names, URL, logo and brief description. Also, the expertise of every partner in the field related to the project.

Project coordinator

Eurecat www.eurecat.org/en Eurecat is the leading Technology Centre of Catalonia. It provides the industrial and business sector with differential technology and advanced expertise, offers solutions to their innovation needs and boosts their competitiveness in a fast-paced environment. One of the key priority areas of the centre focuses on Sustainable Mobility and Big Data Analytics. Eurecat contributes to the project with its experience in fair algorithms, the analysis of social data and decision support systems, as well as autonomous driving, urban connected mobility, electric vehicles and batteries, among others.

Technical coordinator

AITEC www.aitec-intl.com AITEC is a R&D performing SME with the aim to increase the innovation capacity and level of technology of companies to improve their competitiveness in the industrial sector. AITEC is an expert Behaviour Based Safety (BBS) systems and in Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in the transport and logistics field, acting as consultants and auditors.

Participants

DIT www.dit.ie The Dublin Institute of Technology (DIT) is one of Ireland's largest higher education institutions with more than 22,000 students and staff community. The Environmental Sustainability and Health Institute (ESHI), the Learning Training and Technology Centre (LTTTC) and The Applied Intelligence Research Centre (AIRC) participate in the project integrating their scientific and technical expertise with policy and regulatory capability.

UNIVERSITY OF STIRLING

University of Stirling <https://www.stir.ac.uk> The University of Stirling, in Scotland, aims to be at the forefront of research and learning that helps to improve life. The Management Work and Organisation (MWO) Department within the Faculty of the Stirling Management School contributes to the project with its extensive experience in transport and employment research.

 Systematica www.systematica.net Systematica is a planning and engineering consultancy firm specialised in town and transport planning and designing solutions for mobility needs. The consultancy coordinates the identification, acquisition and processing of the Big Data necessary to perform multidisciplinary analysis for each use-case and bringing the perspective from real-time situations, ensuring that the research takes into account all relevant aspects in structuring a proper and useful methodology.

 Edinburgh Napier University www.napier.ac.uk Edinburgh Napier University is a public university in Edinburgh with over 19,500 students. The University participates to the project through its Transport Research Institute, Scotland's largest and longest established transport research group with extensive expertise in socio economics impacts assessment, efficiency analysis, social aspects in gender equality and travel behaviour research.

 University of Belgrade – Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering www.sf.bg.ac.rs The Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering (FTTE), as one of the faculties of the University of Belgrade is the oldest academic and research institution in the field of transportation in Serbia. The FTTE promotes applied research, new methodologies and technologies to provide solutions in the area of transport engineering. It participates to DIAMOND project defining the methodology for efficient and impact assessment and analysis based on productive equity concept.

 Warsaw's Public Transport Authority www.ztm.waw.pl The Warsaw's Public Transport Authority (ZTM) is responsible for planning, organizing and coordination of the city's public transport. The public company is one of DIAMOND's solution testers, with the goal to analyse women's needs and expectations of public transport and get insight about how to improve their services and implement new mobility forms.

 Genre & Ville www.genre-et-ville.org Genre et Ville is an association in defence of gender interests in cities' urban mobility, providing gender urban planning expertise and innovative methodologies to public administrations. In DIAMOND project Genre & Ville will act as a consultant on gender issues, providing good practices through a gender lens.

 Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Catalunya www.fgc.cat/eng/index.asp Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat (FGC) is a suburban railway operator with the aim to contribute to the improvement of Catalonia's mobility. FGC provides to the project their expertise in the design of stations, trains and other railway infrastructure and is responsible for the public transport infrastructure use-case.

 Autolib Vélib <https://autolibmetropole.fr> Autolib "Vélib" is the electric bike and car service operating in Paris metropolitan area, the first public service plan with electric vehicles to be developed in a large European metropolis. As a vehicle-sharing operator, Vélib leads the vehicle-sharing fleet management use-case in order to understand women's needs in the planning of pickup-return points for vehicles.

Hexagon Studio www.hexagonstudio.com.tr Hexagon Studio is a R&D centre delivering unique design and engineering solutions on a national and international scale. Hexagon Studio participates in the definition and running of the specific use-case on adaptation to vehicles to human dynamics and will use DIAMOND's results to develop new algorithms for gender adaptation in vehicle electronics and engine control designs.

RINA www.rina.org RINA is a multinational player supporting clients in the development and management of global initiatives across a wide range of sectors. During the project, RINA is responsible to test project results and bring their expertise to assess possibilities for new certifications including gender design adaptation and standardisation.

**WOMEN AND VEHICLES
IN EUROPE**

WAVE www.waveautos.com WoMen and Vehicles in Europe (WAVE) is an association aimed at everyone (men and women) working in the automotive and mobility sector with two

interdependent goals are: among women - to promote automotive career opportunities, among all in the mobility sector - to open up the sector so that women can provide complementary expertise and a new energy. WAVE contributes to the use-case definition and requirements in terms of employment in the sector, as well as inclusion of gender needs in the design of cars.

External advisory board

Logos of the companies involved in the External Advisory Board: Institut Català de les Dones, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC), The International Transport Forum and Irish Rail. This section will be built once the Advisory Board is established in M6.

DIAMOND' Advisory Board comprise members from the following institutions:

4.2.2.2 Deliverables

This page includes a list of all deliverables to be prepared during the project and will provide access to the executive summary of confidential ones and full-access to the public ones.

4.2.2.3 Resources

List of all project derived results and a brief description. As soon as a resource is ready it will be published and promoted through the website including a download button next to each result description.

Women in transport system model

Evidence-based and living model with multi-dimensional variables allowing a clear picture of behavioural patterns as well as gaps, opportunities and recommendations for a fair and inclusive, safe and secure transport system.

DIAMOND toolbox

Interoperable and user-friendly tool for fairness self-diagnosis and decision support in transport planning able to evaluate the gender inclusion degree of any specific transport planner, as well as provide recommendations on measures and actions for more gender sensitive measures, based on the weaknesses detected.

White paper

White paper for a more fair, inclusive and women-participated mobility and transport system, aiming at recommending concrete measures to enhance women job hiring, adapt training modules to the required skills and support the design and transport's modes and access of infrastructure.

Curriculum Guidelines

CV design guidelines for future transport professionals on how to handle gender needs in transport planning and how to tackle opportunities based on incorporating women talent within the sector.

Novel fair Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) protocols

CSR protocols for a systematic inclusive approach for the transport industry in planning decisions and job offering to be presented to transport entities.

Guidelines for the autonomous automotive sector

Guidelines for automotive companies on how to better adapt autonomous vehicles dynamics to human dynamics taking into account gender to help translate into design recommendations for vehicle adaptive automation.

4.2.2.4 Dissemination

Section including the project's dissemination materials such as publications, presentations or press releases on the project. As soon as dissemination materials are available they will be published to the website and a submenu for each type of dissemination activity will be created.

4.2.2.5 News

This section is for publishing any news related to the project. i.e: about meetings, first results, publications, etc. **News articles will be published regularly by Communication Leader Eurecat with the input of Dissemination leader Dublin Institute of Technology (DIT) and all partners** in order to generate content to feed the project's social media and increase the traffic to the website. News articles will be categorized in self-explanatory categories to facilitate filtering.

On the other hand, partners will be able to contribute to this section with **regular blog posts on the project topics** following guidelines prepared by Communication Leader Eurecat (see **Annex 4**). Partners blog articles will be disseminated widely across DIAMOND’s channels and the basis for regular newsletters.

4.2.2.5.1 Events

This page will include an agenda announcing events where DIAMOND is attending / participating (conferences, fairs, congresses, workshops, etc.) and a list of articles regarding the events attended, type of dissemination activity, target-profile/audience covered, number of attendees and an overview of the feedback received.

This page will be **managed by Dissemination leader DIT, with the support of Communication Leader Eurecat and inputs by all partners.**

4.2.2.6 Contact

This section shows a form for visitors to send comments and questions. The form includes the fields (Name, Surname, Email, Company, Phone, Subject and Message).

On the other hand, the email info@diamond-project.eu has been created and is shown at the website as another way of contact. The project coordinator has access to that email in order to manage all information requests received.

4.2.3 Layout

The website **menu will be available from all pages**, allowing visitors to find the information that they are interested in no matter how they arrived on the site.

The overall design and homepage of the website includes the following elements:

Header

- DIAMOND logo to appear in the header.
- Navigation menu.
- Search button.
- Acces to Social Media platforms (Twitter and Youtube).

Footer

- European Union logo to appear in the footer. Under the logo will appear the phrase ‘This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 824326. This webpage reflects DIAMOND consortium view and neither the European Commission or any associated parties are responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.’
- Link to legal notice.
- Link to privacy statement.
- Link to cookies policy.
- Copyright.

Figure 12: Footer and header structure

4.2.4 *Managing and updating policy*

The website will be developed by Eurecat with the inputs received from all partners in the consortium.

The website will be updated by the Communication Leader Eurecat together with the inputs sent by all partners and specially the support of the Dissemination Leader Dublin Institute of Technology (DIT) every time a new dissemination action is done, a result is achieved, or there is other news worth publishing.

News worthiness will be established at consortium level. The upload policy for public contractual deliverables will be as follows:

1. As soon as the document has been accepted by the Consortium after the internal peer-reviews, an executive summary will be made available.
2. Once the deliverable is also approved by the European Commission, it will be then made formally public in PDF format provided it is at public dissemination level.

4.2.5 *Analytics*

The DIAMOND website will have Matomo installed in the platform's back end to monitoring all the traffic and obtain, periodically, reports about the site's performance. Instead of Google Analytics, Matomo does not compromise data security and privacy, guaranteeing full data ownership and that none of it is ever sent to other services or third parties.

Google Search Console will be used to upload the file robots.txt to make easier for Google Robots the indexation.

4.2.6 *Site hosting, installation & maintenance*

Eurecat is responsible for setting up the website (domain purchase, hosting and Wordpress.org configuration), as well as creating content and design the fixed sections.

As the Communication leader, Eurecat will be responsible for maintaining the site until the project's end and until **two years after and adding content to the website.**

All pages will be optimised for the search engines (SEO), ensuring that DIAMOND website is well positioned in the browsers.

4.2.7 *Data protection*

Eurecat will ensure that DIAMOND website is compliant with all European requirements and standards with regards to data protection and observes the GDPR. Please consult **Annex I** for the website's legal warning, privacy policy and cookies policy.

4.3 *Digital print and printed materials*

DIAMOND project will create communication materials such as an **infosheet** (M4), a **brochure** (M4, updated by M30), a **roll-up** (M4) and a **general project presentation** (M5). These

materials will serve as the project’s business card and will be distributed as widely as possible, including the general public, conferences, workshops and other events, from the beginning of the project.

All these documents will have the online version to be published in the official website and will be distributed among partners digitally for printing.

Figure 13: Design proposals for DIAMOND's promotional materials.

Furthermore, to communicate DIAMOND objectives and results **two videos** will be produced, **one animated video** with motion graphics at the beginning of the project (M6) and a **final project video** based on the project’s use-cases and main outputs ready by M31. The videos will be uploaded on the project’s YouTube channel and website and will have a clear reference to EC support via the Horizon 2020 programme.

On the other hand, a pack of DIAMOND’s project images for partner’s free use will be made available through the project’s shared repository. Partners will be also able to contribute with non-confidential and free-of-use images to be used for internal and external presentations of project-related materials.

4.4 Social media

Eurecat will manage DIAMOND’s social media accounts and its contents described hereinafter. DIAMOND project will count with a **Twitter Channel**, [@DIAMOND_EU](https://twitter.com/DIAMOND_EU), and a **YouTube channel**, account to be created as soon as the first project video is available.

On the other hand, **partners will contribute to spreading the word on their corporate and personal Social Media channels**, including accounts in Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn or Instagram.

The project coordinator will be in charge of notifying the European Commission about possible content of interest to be published through its official social media channels and, whenever possible, will promote the use of **social media complicities between DIAMOND and its sister project TinnGO (Transport Innovation Gender Observatory)**.

4.4.1 Twitter

Twitter is the 2.0 tool most used by the European Commission to now disseminate the H2020 program, so its creation has full meaning. The account will be managed by Eurecat with the support of project partners for the correct management of the account.

DIAMOND's main objective on Twitter is to reach its **raising awareness** on the current role of women as transport professionals and end-users of transport and mobility services, as well as **promoting the project's results to the specific key stakeholders and the broad audience**. Twitter allows to reach directly targeted audiences from validated professional accounts.

Figure 14: View of DIAMOND's Twitter account

4.4.1.1 Account management

Eurecat will create a **bimonthly content plan** to be disseminated through Twitter. All consortium partners can propose contents (text, images, videos...) to be distributed for this channel and can spread the word through their own channels.

DIAMOND's Communication Leader Eurecat will use **Hootsuite** for programming tweets and shorten URLs, a management tool that facilitates the publication of contents and easy monitors the activity in social media.

Comments and answers will be managed manually, in order to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content.

4.4.1.2 Strategy

When creating and publishing content on the networks about the project, Eurecat and the rest of the partners will consider the following recommendations in order to maximize the impact of the messages.

The strategy mixes marketing content, branding and influence actions to maximise DIAMOND's project impact and encourage market uptake, to secure a critical mass of early adopters among consumers.

4.4.1.2.1 Content strategy includes:

- Disseminate the organization of meetings, reviews, and milestones including text and photos if possible.
- Content curation: sharing news about women as transport professionals, European transport systems, mobility & mobility tracking, mobility modes (especially the ones represented in the use-cases: railways, autonomous vehicles and car & bike sharing services), mobility and gender, transport and mobility policies.
- Disseminate the videos made for the project (to make the project more accessible/understandable) better reach users thanks to a character and a specific plot.
- Sharing news and blog posts published in the website to increase traffic to the website.
- Promote through social media the project results (white paper, guidelines, etc.) to increase the number of downloads.
- To increase the reach of the tweets, it is proposed the frequent use of the following hashtags, usual in other areas within the scope of the project: #DiamondH2020 #WomenInTransport #women #transport #genderbalance #gender #mobility #equality #DataScience #BigData #DataAnalytics #ResearchImpactEu #H2020Transport #Horizon2020 #H2020 #CEFTransport #EUtransport
- Mention project partners when publishing news about them to promote likes and retweets from partners.

4.4.1.2.2 Branding strategy includes:

- Twitter covering in fairs in international trade shows and fairs where DIAMOND is presented using the official hashtag of the event (e.g. Transport Research Arena #TRA2020, International Conference on Travel Behaviour Research #IATBR2018, International Conference on Computational Social Science #IC2S2).
- DIAMOND's Twitter official account will be referenced in the partner's corporate accounts for a broader reach of the project.

4.4.1.2.3 Influencers' strategy:

- Regularly mention @EU_H2020 @EuScienceInnov @transport_EU @inea_eu @EU_commission in order to get a bigger impact when project news or information about results is published.
- Identify and mention influencers in the field of research on women in transport, gender issues, data analytics in the transport sector, etc.
- Identification of stakeholder's accounts to promote follow-back and to increase the number of DIAMOND followers.
- Media will be mentioned if they are publishing information about the project.

4.4.1.3 Following and followers

Our reputation on Twitter depends on the number of users we follow. There must be a balanced number between our followers and the users we follow. Otherwise, it is considered that the tool is being misused, since the objective is to share knowledge bidirectionally.

Therefore, DIAMOND will follow people and organizations related to the project's topic (transport, women, data analytics). At the first stage of the project, DIAMOND's Twitter account will follow all project partners, as well of institutions, centres and professionals in the field of the project, which will be identified during the first months of the project. The media, as well as Twitter profiles of reference bloggers, covering the project topic will also be followed.

We will avoid followers with an offensive avatar (for example, pornographic, racist) or spammers, which we will block.

4.4.1.4 First battery of tweets

During the first months of the project, is proposed a content strategy on more generic tweets about the project, as the ones below. As the project is being executed, content on specific results, news and posts and specific advances in each of the project's use-cases will be disseminated through Twitter.

Figure 15: First battery of tweets.

4.4.1.5 Analytics

A profile in Twitter Analytics will be activated in order measure Twitter’s KPIs (please view Communication KPIs section for more information) and other data about the account activity. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

4.4.2 YouTube

The European Commission has recommended the use of resources as the storytelling for putting objectives and results of the research projects closer to the general public. This narrative technique is based on the narrative of a story and it is used on marketing strategies to better reach users thanks to a character and a plot.

Following these recommendations, the videos produced within the project (M6 and M30) will be published in a **YouTube channel** and will be shared on the website and project’s Twitter for a broader impact.

On the other hand, the account will serve as a content repository of all audio-visual content that may be produced during the project.

4.4.3 Partners’ channels

Each partner will transmit DIAMOND news and results through their personal and corporate social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and Instagram), including press releases, notices about events, promotional materials and other contents published on www.diamond-project.eu or in DIAMOND’s twitter account.

DIAMOND’s partners impact in social media channels will reach more than **116,800 users on Twitter**, more than **148,600 on LinkedIn** and more than **109.900 Facebook** followers.

The corporate accounts to be used are:

Table 1: Partners’ social media channels.

PARTNER			
Eurecat	https://www.facebook.com/Eurecatorg/	@Eurecat_news	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eurecat/
AITEC	https://www.facebook.com/AITEC-212175395463594/	@aitecintl	https://www.linkedin.com/company/aitec-intl/?trk=hb_tab_compy_id_2195871

<u>Dublin Institute of Technology</u>	https://www.facebook.com/DublinInstituteOfTechnology/	@WeAreTUDublin	https://www.linkedin.com/school/dublin-institute-of-technology/
<u>University of Stirling</u>	https://www.facebook.com/universityofstirling/ https://www.facebook.com/stirlingmanagementschool	@stiruni @RonaldMcQuaid @stir_Research	https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-stirling/
<u>Systematica</u>	NA	@systematica	https://www.linkedin.com/company/systematica-srl/?originalSubdomain=it
<u>Edinburgh Napier University</u>	NA	@EdNapierTRI	NA
<u>University of Belgrade - FTTE</u>	https://www.facebook.com/SaobraajniFakultetI950/	@SF_Beograd	https://www.linkedin.com/company/faculty-of-transport-and-traffic-engineering/about/
<u>Zarząd Transportu Miejskiego Warszawa</u>	https://www.facebook.com/wtp.warszawa	@WTP Warszawa	NA
<u>Genre & Ville</u>	https://www.facebook.com/Genre-et-Ville-286745504777426/	@GenreetVille	NA
<u>Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Catalunya</u>	https://www.facebook.com/fgcferrocarrils/	@FGC @FGCcorporatiu	NA
<u>AUTOLIB VÉLIB</u>	NA	NA	NA

<u>Hexagon Studio</u>	https://www.facebook.com/hexagonstudio/	@hexagonstudiotr	https://www.linkedin.com/company/hexagon-studio/
<u>RINA</u>	NA	@RINA1861	https://www.linkedin.com/company/rina/
<u>WAVE</u>	NA	@WaveAutos	https://www.linkedin.com/company/wave-women-and-vehicles-europe/

4.5 Media relations

Press releases will be **written and sent at regular intervals throughout the project** (two press releases per year) focusing on the release of research results, tools and project materials, meetings, attendance to specialised events, conferences, etc. and connected with newsworthy initiatives when possible, such as the Women’s International Day or the European Mobility Week.

All press releases will be distributed among partners in English, who, after providing feedback, will be able to adapt them in their corporate language and make them circulate throughout their communication channels and sent to their media database.

Apart from consortium press releases, country-focused press releases or press releases oriented for a specific stakeholder group can be elaborated by partners, after informing the Project Coordinator. Also partners can consider interview-offerings and a press conference at the end of the project to show the main project results to media.

In the framework of the project, a **database with the contact details of partners’ communication officers** will be created, to facilitate the review of the media materials, coordinate the sending of the press releases and increase impact.

On the other hand, a **database with specialized media covering transport and gender issues** will be created, primarily with outlets located in the partner’s countries Spain, Ireland, UK, Italy, Serbia, Poland, France and Turkey. Communication Leader Eurecat will contact key specialized media and include them in their media database. Press releases will be also distributed in paid platforms such as AlphaGalileo.

An initial calendar of press releases to be written is as follows:

Table 2: Press releases tentative calendar.

Month	Topic	Partner responsible
M3	Start of the project	EUT

M9	Data Collection Campaign	AITEC
M11 /M23	DIAMOND first results on European Mobility Week	TBD
M5 / M17 / M29	Women's Day	TBD
M28	Testing DIAMOND tools	FGC, HEX, VELIB, AITEC
M35	DIAMOND results	EUT

4.6 Community building and email marketing

Communication Leader Eurecat, together with SYSTEMATICA, in charge of the project's Data Collection Campaign to engage with final users, will create a community of people interested in DIAMOND results through posting the **online questionnaire for its purpose on the project's website for data collection and actively promote the questionnaire across Social Media.**

All members of the DIAMOND group will **receive periodic information** on the project and results to be downloaded (White Paper, toolbox, etc.). Email marketing campaigns / newsletters will be sent out 1 time during the project's first year (M12), 2 on the 2nd year (M18, M24) and 3 times on the last year (M28, M32, M36), as the first year will be devoted on gaining newsletter subscribers.

DIAMOND newsletters and other project results (white paper, CV guidelines, etc.) will be shared with all **Women In Transport Platform** members as best practices for equal opportunities for women and men in the transport sector.

Additionally, information about DIAMOND project will be included to partners' newsletters or corporate publications, such as Eurecat's monthly corporate newsletter addressed to external audience, with more than 15,000 subscribers.

Communication KPIs

The following table introduces an initial set of DIAMOND Key performance Indicators (KPIs) for assessing the communication activities. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

Table 3: Communication KPIs

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	Target by the end of the project
Media	Number of press releases	Proof of publication and reporting in reports / project meetings	>6
	Number of articles, sector press with project acknowledgements	Proof of publication and reporting in reports / project meetings	>50
Website	Number of web visits	Matomo Analytics	>4.500
	Number Pages Viewed		>10.000
	Number page / session		>1.0
	Number users		>2.000
	Avg. session time		>1.0 min
	Number downloads model models	Website Analytics	>50
	Downloads DIAMOND toolbox		>50
	Downloads White Paper “Women in Transport”		>300
Downloads Curriculum Guidelines	>300		

Social Media (Twitter)	Number Followers	Twitter Analytics	>150
	Number Tweets		>150
	Twitter Impressions		>35.000
	Number mentions		>15
Social Media (Mentions in partners accounts).	Number of posts	Monthly follow up (quantitative)	>20
	Number of Likes		>50
	Number Shares / Retweets		>10

Calendar

Table 4: Communication actions calendar.

Action	M1 Nov 18	M2	M3 Jan 19	M4	M5 Mar 19	M6	M7 May 19	M8	M9 Jul 19	M10	M11 Sep 19	M12	M13 Nov 19	M14	M15 Jan 20	M16	M17 Mar 20	M18
Project logo	X																	
Word and Power Point template	X																	
Twitter channel creation	X																	
Visual Identity Guidebook		X																
Website Content			X															
DI.3 Communication Plan			X															
Twitter bimonthly content calendars				X		X		X		X		X		X		X		X
Website Creation				X														
Newsletter signup form creation				X														
Infosheet				X														
Brochure				X														
Rollup				X														
Poster Layout					X													
General project presentation					X													
Press release (Women's Day / project kick off)					X												X	
Website Update					X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
1 st animated video						X												
Creation YouTube channel						X												
Data Collection questionnaire promotion on Website & SM									X	X	X	X						
Press release (Data Collection)									X									
Press release (European Mobility Week) - tentative											X							

	M19 May 20	M20	M21 Jul 20	M22	M23 Sep 20	M24	M25 Nov 20	M26	M27 Jan 21	M28	M29 Mar 21	M30	M31 May 21	M32	M33 Jul 21	M34	M35 Sep 21	M36
D9.5 First year dissemination and exploitation report (provide input)												X						
1st project newsletter												X						
2nd project newsletter																		X
Website Update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Brochure Updated												X						
Twitter content calendars		X		X		X		X		X		X		X		X		X
2nd video (results)													X					
Press release (European Mobility Week) - tentative					X													
D9.6 Second year dissemination and exploitation report (provide input)						X												
3rd project newsletter						X												
Press release (testing DIAMOND tools)										X								
4th project newsletter										X								
Pres Release (Women's Day) - tentative											X							
5th project newsletter														X				
6th project newsletter																		X
Press release (DIAMOND results)																		X
D9.6 Third year dissemination and exploitation report (provide input)																		X

Annex

I. Privacy policy

In compliance with Law 34/2002 of 11 July on Information Society and Electronic Commerce Services, the User is informed that the owner of the website www.diamond-project.eu is FUNDACIÓ EURECAT, whose identification information is as follows:

Registered office: Av. Universitat Autònoma, 23

Post code: 08290

Town/City: Cerdanyola del Vallès

Province: Barcelona

CIF: G66210345

E-mail: info@eurecat.org

Registry data: Registered in the Foundations Registry of the Generalitat de Catalunya with the number 2826.

Access to the Website

This legal notice regulates the access and use of the website by Users and aims to inform about the services and products of the entity and allow general access for all Internet users.

Any person who accesses or uses the Website is considered a User and accepts, without reservations of any kind, each and every one of these general conditions, as well as of other special conditions that, if applicable, govern the use of the Portal or the services linked to it.

The user must carefully read the Legal Notice and the Privacy and Cookies Policies when they intend to use the Website, since FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right to make, at any time and without prior notice, any modification or update of the contents and services, of the present provisions for access and use and, in general, of all the elements that comprise the design and configuration of its Website. If you do not accept the conditions of access and use, please refrain from using the Website and its content.

Use of the Website

The User undertakes to make diligent use of the Website, as well as the information relating to its services and/or activities, in full compliance with the applicable regulations, ethics and generally accepted good practices and law and order, the conditions of access and use and any other conditions established on the Website.

In addition, the user agrees to refrain from using any of the content for illegal purposes or effects, prohibited in this document, which may be harmful to the rights and interests of third parties, or that in any way may damage, disable, overload, deteriorate or prevent the normal use of the content (hardware and software) of other Users or of any Internet user in general.

Operation of the website

In the event of non-compliance with the conditions of the Legal Notice, or the Privacy and Cookies Policies, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right to limit, suspend and/or exclude access to its website, adopting any technical measure necessary in this respect. FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will do everything possible to keep the website in good working order, preventing faults, or repairing them and keeping the contents up to date. However, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT does not guarantee the availability and continuity of access to the Website or the absence of errors in the content.

Liability

The User is solely liable for the use that they may make of any information or mechanism of the Website.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will not be liable for any damage to the hardware and/or software of the User that may arise from access and use of the Website. Likewise, it will be not liable for damages or losses that may be caused by access and/or use of the information on the Website, and specifically those that may occur in computer systems or those caused by computer viruses/attacks, crashes, interruptions, absence or defects in connectivity and/or the Internet.

The User will be liable for the damages and/or losses that FUNDACIÓ EURECAT may suffer as a result of the breach of any of the obligations to which they are subject to through this Legal Notice, applicable regulations and the Privacy and Cookies Policies.

Policy on links

a) Web linking:

Third parties who intend to include a link on a website to this website must comply with current legislation and may not host content that is inappropriate, illegal, pornographic, violent, etc.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will in no case be liable for the content of that Website, nor promote, guarantee, supervise or recommend the content therein.

If the linking Website fails to comply with any of the above aspects, it will be obliged to delete the link immediately.

b) Linking website:

This Website may include links to third-party websites that allow the User to access them. Nonetheless, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT is not liable for the content of these linked websites, but rather the User will be responsible for accepting and verifying access each time they connect.

These links or mentions have a use that does not imply the support, approval, commercialization or any relationship of this website and the persons or entities that own the site where they are located.

Intellectual and industrial property rights of the content:

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT, or its licensors, are holders of all intellectual property rights over the Contents of the Website, understood as all the designs, databases, underlying computer programs

(source code, included), as well as the different elements that make up the Website (texts, graphics, photographs, videos, colours, etc.), structure, layout, etc. The trademarks and trade names ("distinctive signs") are owned by FUNDACIÓ EURECAT or the licensors.

The use of the Website by the User does not imply the transfer of any intellectual or industrial property rights. The User is totally prohibited from reproducing, copying, distributing, making available or publicly communicating, transforming or modifying the Contents or Distinctive Signs in any way, unless the authorization of the owner of the corresponding rights is granted or it is legally permitted.

Applicable legislation

The Legal Notice will be governed and interpreted in accordance with Spanish legislation.

Any conflict that may arise from accessing the website will be submitted to the relevant courts or tribunals for resolution in accordance with consumer and user regulations.

Contact

For any questions or comments on this Legal Notice you can contact us at legal@eurecat.org.

2. Cookies policy

Informational banner

This website uses cookies to collect statistical information on user browsing and improve its services with their preferences generated from their browsing patterns.

Learn more about who we are, how you can contact us and how we process personal data in our Privacy Policy.

What are cookies and why do we use them on the website?

A cookie is a small text file that is created in the user's device when accessing certain websites to store and retrieve any kind of information. Usually cookies store information related to the browsing that is carried out from your device.

Some cookies are strictly necessary for the operation of the webpage while some others are used for other purposes. Some cookies are placed by this website, while some others are placed by third party services like social media providers. Also, depending on the time they remain in your device, can be divided into session or permanent cookies.

We can store on your device those cookies that are strictly necessary for the operation of this site. For all other types of cookies we need your consent.

What type of cookies does the website use?

This website only uses NECESSARY and STATISTICS cookies.

Necessary cookies make this website usable by enabling basic functions like page navigation and access to secure areas of the website. This website can't work properly without necessary cookies.

Statistics cookies help us to understand how visitors interact with websites by collecting and reporting information anonymously. We use statistics cookies provided by the open-source analytics platform MATOMO, stored in our own servers.

More details about the cookies we use:

Necessary

Name	Provider	Purpose	Expiry	Type
_icl_current_language	diamond-project.eu	Stores current language	Session	HTTP
viewed_cookie_policy	diamond-project.eu	Stores user visit to privacy policy	1 year	HTTP

Statistics

Name	Provider	Purpose	Expiry	Type
XXX	diamond-project.eu		Session	HTTP
XXXX	diamond-project.eu	User unique ID that is used to generate statistical data on how the visitor	13 months	HTTP

uses the
website.

How can the user disable the browser cookies?

You can configure your browser to not accept the use of cookies, in which case the personalization of the experience will not work as well as some parts of the website. Browsing experience may be less efficient but still possible.

The user can configure their browser to not accept the use of cookies, in which case the personalization of the experience would not apply. If this configuration is selected, it may not be possible to access certain parts of the website, as it may cause less efficient browsing.

Most browsers currently allow the user to configure whether they want to accept cookies and which ones. These parameters are usually found in the “parameters” or “preferences” of the browser’s menu.

Here the instructions for configuring cookies in the main browsers:

Chrome: Settings -> Show advanced settings -> Privacy -> Content settings. For more information, you can check Google support or the browser’s Help.

Firefox: Tools -> Options -> Privacy -> History -> Custom Settings. For more information, you can check Mozilla support or the browser’s Help.

Internet Explorer: Tools -> Internet Options -> Privacy -> Settings. For more information, you can check Microsoft support or the browser’s Help.

Safari: Preferences -> Security. For more information, you can check Apple support or the browser’s Help.

Additional information

For more information on the use of cookies and how to block them, go to www.allaboutcookies.org, www.youronlinechoices.eu. If you have any questions or comments about our use of cookies, please contact us at legal@eurecat.org.

3. Legal notice

Who is the data controller for your personal data?

Data controller: FUNDACIÓ EURECAT (“EURECAT”)

Tax ID number: G66210345

Address: Parc Tecnològic del Vallès. Avinguda Universitat Autònoma, 23 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès

Email address: legal@eurecat.org

Telephone: +34 93 238 14 00

Data protection delegate contact: dpo@eurecat.org

For what purpose will be process your personal data?

Data received through the contact form will be used for the exclusive purpose of managing your queries or requests.

If you agree to receive commercial communication, the purpose of the processing will be to keep you informed of the latest news affecting Fundació Eurecat.

On our website, there may be forms that collect your data for specific purposes. In these circumstances, you will be subject to the specific terms applicable to each case.

It is mandatory to provide all the information requested in the forms on the website?

The user must complete the fields marked as “required”. Failure to complete the required personal information or to partially do so may mean that Fundació Eurecat cannot meet your requests and, consequently, Fundació Eurecat will be exempt from any liability for the non-provision or incomplete provision of the requested services.

The personal data provided by the User to Fundació Eurecat must be up to date so that the information in our records is current and without errors. The user will be liable for the veracity of the data provided.

For how long will be retain your personal data?

Personal data will be retained for the duration of the purpose for which it was collected and while its erasure is not requested and consent is not revoked.

What is the lawful basis for our processing of your personal data?

The lawful basis for the processing of your data is the consent provided through acceptance of the data processing clause.

To what recipients will your data be communicated?

Personal data received through the forms of the website will be shared with members of the project for the exclusive purpose of managing your query or request and be able to send you the latest news about the project through periodic newsletters.

Your data will not be passed on to third-party companies, unless there is a legal obligation to do so. Should this case arise, authorisation will be sought first from the concerned parties.

What are your rights regarding your personal data?

The user may exercise their right to access their personal data, to request the rectification of inaccurate data and, where applicable, to request the data be erased if it is no longer necessary for the purposes for which it was collected. The user may also exercise their right to data portability and to the restriction of or opposition to the processing of their data, in certain circumstances and for reasons related to their specific situation.

The user also has the right to revoke their consent at any time, without any retroactive effect on the processing of their personal data carried out until that point.

The user may exercise the aforementioned rights, under the terms provided for in current legislation, at the registered office of Fundació Eurecat or request to do so by sending an email to legal@eurecat.org.

Should the user not receive a satisfactory response and should they wish to make a complaint or obtain more information on any of these rights, they may contact the Spanish Data Protection Agency (www.agpd.es - C/ Jorge Juan, 6, Madrid).

What security measures has the institution implemented?

Fundació Eurecat declares that it has implemented the necessary technical and organisational security measures that guarantee the security of the User's personal data and avoid its alteration, loss, processing and/or unauthorised access considering the state of technology, the nature of the stored data and the risks to which it is exposed, whether from human action or from the physical or natural environment, in accordance with the provisions of current regulations.

Social media

DIAMOND, project coordinated by Fundació Eurecat has a profile on Twitter for publishing and disseminating information about the services provided through the website, interacting with users and acting as a customer service and social interaction channel.

The following are links to the privacy policies of the social networks on which DIAMOND an active profile:

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/en/privacy>

4. Blog posts guidelines

We envision 2 types of articles to be posted on the website according to its length: short and large ones.

- a. **Short articles:** are up to 500 words and can be written for the general public or for the scientific and academic community. Normally this kind of articles would include one or more hyperlinks to other content (either written by us or by other party not related to DIAMOND Project).
- b. **Large articles:** standalone articles that are from 700 to 1000 words long. Aimed to the scientific and academic community but can be also read by interested persons from the general public (please try to limit acronyms and specialized jargon or explain it somewhere within the article itself). It might contain links as well but mostly to support material or cited sources.

Both types of articles should be supported with at least one picture, diagram, graphic or maybe more.

- More scientific kind of articles will be well dressed with graphics and diagrams which support the text. These diagrams or graphics should be provided by the author since they are closely related to the content and would be difficult to produce otherwise.
- General images would be provided by Euratec as DIAMOND's Communication Leader. If you need specific ones, you can either provide them yourself or work with us to identify a good image.
- We will set up a small bank of images in Sharepoint to be used for this purpose.

The **topics recommended** for these articles are:

- Women in transport
- Gender and Transport / Mobility
- Women as professionals of the transport. Sector.
- Transport & Transportation
- Mobility & Mobility Tracking
- Multimodality
- Behaviors & Activities (related to transport and mobility)

- Physical and social preference when choosing transport
- Gender perceptions around mobility and commuting
- Transport and Mobility Policies
- Public transport infrastructures
- Autonomous Transport Systems
- Vehicle sharing systems.
- Mobility habits in large cities
- Fairness algorithms.

